

Thematic Quote Clustering

(All Participants)

LEGEND

Identifier	Meaning
P## (P01, P02,, P10)	Participant 01, Participant 02,, Participant 10
T#-P# (T1-P1)	Theme 1 – Pattern 1
Design-## (Design-01)	Design Recommendations - 01
Cross-Cutting-P# (Cross-Cutting-P1)	Cross-Cutting Patterns - Pattern 1
R#.# (R5.1)	Relationships Between Primary Themes – 5.1 (Please see Cross_Participant_Synthesis)
Div	Divergent Pattern
Red	Possible Theme 1*
Green	Possible Theme 2*
Blue	Possible Theme 3*
Cyan	Possible Theme 4*
Yellow	Possible Theme 5*
Magenta	Possible Theme 6*
Quote... Quote (I know people always get the way of least resistance. Any game you take, whatever designer has made up (■) people just gonna storm it in three seconds if they can, and I'm	The left side of the (■) represents the first part of the quote, and the right side represents the second part. The parts are, in most cases, different sentences rather than a single continuous sentence in the participant transcription.

not different in this regard honestly.)	
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Note: (*) means it could overlap with other themes or other patterns. The colors are used for better readability, but they may not always be consistent, as a single quote might appear in multiple themes or patterns. Another important thing to consider is that, even if we remove the colors, the probable themes and patterns can still communicate through the legends we discussed above.

P01

Q1: Quote: "I noticed that in the PC version there's a wobble which is really cool, and it was not in VR, and I think it's good that it wasn't in VR. I think if you would also leave it in VR version, I would feel sick."

Q2: Quote: "I would love it to have the same effect for elevator because essentially it's the same button... everything else does have this green effect of activation."

Q3: Quote: "Smashing button was more fun... I think when something is up there and it's yellow and you just want to push it, this is just classic. I think, of virtual games—some interactivity. I think it's just natural to poke something or to push something. On the other hand, pressing X is just basically a button, that's it." (T5-P1, Design-04)

Q4: Quote: "I would love it to have the same effect for elevator because essentially it's the same button. I press it, it's green, I know it's activated. There was a sound that I registered, but at first I wasn't sure I pressed it. I'm like, 'Okay, is it working?' Oh, I hear the sound, it is working. Just a small thing—because everything else does have this green effect of activation." (T5-P2, Design-05)

Q5: Quote: "EMP was lacking some kind of visual effect because it was just the sound and I don't understand, 'Okay, what happened?' I didn't even get this EMP because I didn't read the description or something. There's some sound happening but no visuals. Like is it around me? Is it some wave? Is it only front? Is it all the sides? Maybe add some simple wave that I would also love to see where does it end." (T5-P2, Design-05)

Q6: Quote: "It was more fun to climb the ladder, even though I had troubles at first. At some point I had fun climbing the ladder actively rather than just pressing button and waiting on the PC. On the PC, I just press a button and then I just move up and it's like... okay, five seconds, ten seconds, okay I'm up. So it was quite dull." (T1-P3)

Q7: Quote: "I didn't find overall the sneaking mechanic much different. They felt the same."

Q8: Quote: "Even though for school children of 13-15 years old that play, they just naturally do it really easily and I can't wrap my head around it. So I don't know, maybe it's just me."

Q9: Quote: "I pressed it accidentally I think during climbing or something and it activated, and I was a bit confused."

Q10: Quote: "I thought I would climb ladder like this, and without your input I wouldn't have guessed it. I think I would just be stuck probably."

Q11: Quote: "Zipline, when I'm in VR, I press the button and I go backwards and I need to rotate myself, and that, at first it felt like 'huh.' I kind of expected just in my subconscious that I would rotate somehow automatically. That happens on PC—when I press the button, I do rotate my head towards it."

Q12: Quote: "I don't think I felt any additional pressure in VR than in PC, again, because I quickly realized that they're really easy."

Q13: Quote: "I think in VR it felt higher and more around you. I think it was of course more immersive in some way. When you're there, it does feel like, Oh, it's really high." (T1-P1, T1-P2)

Q14: Quote: "I didn't find the control with the ladder intuitive for me personally, even though it's subject to controversy, of course. I thought I would climb ladder like this, and without your input I wouldn't have guessed it. I think I would just be stuck probably." (T4-P2, Design-01)

Q15: Quote: "I think there was a bit of discomfort from just headset itself because of this strap and everything, because this basic strap is, you know, it's bad." (T2-P1)

Q16: Quote: "So I felt like the hand of God gets me and just places me there—like the cat mother gets her kitten and just places them."

Q17: Quote: "Traversal—the movement. As I said, the strafe to sides and the camera rotation. I think this is why it was comfortable and more natural to play for me on PC, and I completed it faster just because of that." (T3-P3, T4-P1)

Q18: Quote: "I think the last third or quarter of the ladder you don't climb because you have this automatic animation of getting up, which for me was a bit like 'huh.' I felt a bit disoriented by it because I expected that I need to go up to the top, but then in the last quarter it just teleports me without my control. So I felt like the hand of God gets me and just places me there—like the cat mother gets her kitten and just places them."

Q19: Quote: "I would rather play it in VR, even though I said that PC version was more overall kind of nice. I think I would prefer a bit edited and better version of VR. In this particular case I felt like it was more comfortable to play on PC, but I would love to play in VR because I feel like this interactivity is good for VR. These ladders and tapping and pushing buttons—it's all working well. You see your hands." (T2-P2, T2-P4, T6-P1, Cross-Cutting-P1)

Q20: Quote: "I know people always get the way of least resistance. Any game you take, whatever designer has made up... people just gonna storm it in three seconds if they can, and I'm not different in this regard honestly."

Q21: Quote: "I didn't, even though I have the fear of heights, I didn't feel it in this game in particular. You saw me jumping down from there because there's no fall damage, and I cheated my way a little bit there." (Div, Cross-Cutting-P3)

Q22: Quote: "I immediately wanted to strafe left and right like I do here, but I couldn't for some reason on VR. I can only move front and back and that really disturbed me. I'm like, 'Okay, I really need to move sides' because this is what in most VR games you do." (T3-P1)

Q23: Quote: "I immediately wanted to strafe left and right like I do here, but I couldn't for some reason on VR. I can only move front and back and that really disturbed me." (Design-02)

Q24: Quote: "I think what was limiting my experience in VR was not the headset itself but the cable. Because when you're connected to the cable—I mean, I also developed some stuff, I know it's annoying, and I think you need some special straps for it not to be annoying."

Because I immediately wanted to rotate and then I feel it, and I know that if I unplug it, it will just break the game because it launches from the PC."

Q25: Quote: "I mean, I also developed some stuff, I know it's annoying."

Q26: Quote: "I think it was the zipline. It was cool. It was also unexpected. But even with the problem, yeah, even that, it was cool."

Q27: Quote: "Ladder. The lever pulling also. Because in PC version you just press the button and that's it. But on VR you actually do the stuff, which is cool."

Q28: Quote: "Also, with the right stick, the movement was choppy—you move and it's choppy. Whereas on PC it's smooth. I also would love maybe in VR game to be smoother motion of right stick." (T3-P2, Design-03)

Q29: Quote: "*Because for example, I think that even when I scan—I use this scan and I see enemies—and even when I disable them and I scan, I still see them in the normal state, and I can't understand whether they're just standing or I deactivated them.*" (T5-P3)

Q30: Quote: "*I think these controllers are just like gamepads, they're really similar, they have the same buttons even. Just naturally I wanted to move, and on PC version I could do it but in VR I couldn't.*" (R5.3)

P02

Q1: Quote: "No, I had no idea this existed." [Regarding vignette comfort effect]

Q2: Quote: "Oh, yeah, for example, I didn't even remember that part actually until you said it. Because it was just once, um, unlike the other interactions, and, um, it was pretty easy for me in the both versions." (Interview)

Q3: Quote: "I mean this is just a master project, and like not a commercial game, and like you have a lot of time constraints, and you're doing this alone, and stuff. So, it's, it's not like you know a game that you would play always... I don't expect them at all, so I wouldn't, I don't know, I, I mean, I don't see the reason to comment on those stuff just saying." (Interview)

Q4: Quote: "Yeah, but I mean that one actually didn't feel like so much different for example." (Interview)

Q5: Quote: "I think I understood that I have to pull from the sides and not the bars, but, like, if you didn't tell me, I could actually, like, okay, like, maybe it's the bars, I could feel like that." (Design-01)

Q6: Quote: "For this particular game, I would say you can compromise the, like, I mean you can choose the VR version. But some of them needs to be a bit shorter maybe, some of these interactions, and it depends, like, if it's like super uncomfortable, I would prefer the PC one for example." (T2-P2, T2-P3, T2-P4)

Q7: Quote: "The first ladder is just very tall, and, like, you have to do it, like, for a very long time... okay, how, how long is the ladder? But, I think, you can go, I mean, look up and see, and it's also a nice thing."

Q8: Quote: "It was fun. I mean, it's, like, a very simple interaction. But even, like, just the fact that you can do that. Just do this, and it feels like a real button, instead of going there and pressing the keyboard or whatever. It's definitely, yeah, the button. It's better in VR." (T5-P1, Design-04)

Q9: Quote: "Just, like, the, when you go on top, it automatically put you there. It was a bit disturbing for me because, maybe it was just too fast or something. But, yeah, that part was just a bit off-putting."

Q10: Quote: "Um, yes, but, like, the game needs to be ten times shorter, and like, yeah, and if you find a way to actually make the crouching uncomfortable, maybe, like, it would be just standing and sitting." (Interview)

Q11: Quote: "I mean, it's both, like, because of the VR headset, you are, like, seeing literally the first person and, like, feeling like you are the person. But also, like, I think some of the interactions, such as the ladder and all the other stuff, like, feel more like in real life, definitely, compared to the PC. Because in the PC, you just press a keyboard or something. But, like, the VR one, you both, like, grab it, like, hold it, you press a button too, but you also, like, move your arms and stuff accordingly, like, like, in the, in real life movement." (T1-P1)

Q12: Quote: "Yeah, yeah, I understand, but I think you explained. I don't remember what you exactly said, but I think I understood that I have to pull from the sides and not the bars, but, like, if you didn't tell me, I could actually, like, okay, like, maybe it's the bars, I could feel like that." (T4-P2, Design-01)

Q13: Quote: "Um, the thing is, I always played games. Like, I mean, I usually play games on keyboard and mouse. So, when I was playing in PC, it was the basic stuff, like, moving and, like, pressing just a button and something, like, those stuff were a bit more intuitive than VR." (T4-P1)

Q14: Quote: "The ladder one was cool. I thought, oh, this is actually so cool to do it like this. Because also it was the first interaction that actually like changed a lot in the VR version, and felt realistic." (T1-P3)

Q15: Quote: "Uh, I didn't like the moving in VR, which is always a tricky thing, because, like, whether it's teleportation or just, like, moving like that is just, like, um, annoying. Maybe if it was just, you can, um, the turning around was not, you know, like, snapping, but also smooth, maybe would feel a bit better, moving wise." (T3-P2, Design-03)

Q16: Quote: "I guess it also depends on the game. Because for this particular game, you created thinking like you are gonna do it for both PC and VR, and it can not be done if you start with just PC for example. You can't really take a PC game right now, and make it VR... Because of the mechanics and stuff." (Interview)

Q17: Quote: "I mean, I guess VR, because it's more exciting than the PC one." (T6-P1)

Q18: Quote: "Because of the controllers, too, actually, because the moving controllers, and, like, in PC, I could move, actually, very fast, and, like, disable them, and I wouldn't mind, you know. But in the other one I had to change the direction, and stuff, and it, I couldn't really get into that, uh, control, uh, very fast, so, it felt a bit anxious." (T3-P3)

Q19: Quote: "I felt a bit of motion sickness, yes... Walking. Not all the time, but at some parts walking, and maybe the ladder or the monkey bar a bit too, not a lot, not super disturbing." (T2-P1)

Q20: Quote: "Um, like, the height-wise, it does affect, especially when you're, like, in the monkey bar or, like, when you're, um, in the zipline and stuff. It, it affects, I think, in the VR, it, um, feels taller, and, like, you, uh, look down and, like, it feels like you can actually fall,

and it's, like, you're in the actual height, and that's, in the sense, it affects the dystopian thingy, I would say." (T1-P2, Div)

P03

Q1: Quote: "I guess the PC version, it felt almost a bit redundant, because you just press one button, or you usually, in usual games, don't need to do much to climb a ladder, and in VR, it was more, oh God, I really need to, Um, I need to put effort into climbing, but it was just a completely different thing." (T1-P3)

Q2: Quote: "But, like, from the immersion, everything is just bigger. Because, on PC, everything is just on your small screen. But, in VR, it's just, I know it's just the default Unreal Engine models. But, if it's something, if it's life size, it's just more threatening." (T1-P2)

Q3: Quote: "In the PC version? To be honest, in general, the PC version did not have that of a big impact on me, compared to the VR version. Most stuff I remember from the VR version because it was just more impressive, but the PC version, I guess... hard to tell, nothing specific, to be honest. Because all the interactions seem very familiar from other games I played." (T6-P3)

Q4: Quote: "Um, not the game, like, no, just, sometimes I get a headache, but from the headset itself, from the weight, or because I did not adjust properly, or whatever, but not from the game itself." (T2-P1)

Q5: Quote: "Maybe even if you only move your head for some centimeters, maybe in VR, you turn around for, for even more degrees."

Q6: Quote: "For me, I had no problem with the height itself, like that I was in fear or something, or in fear of my character, with the PC version. But it was just more immersive in VR, because the PC, like the desktop version, the PC version was just not, you didn't really care about the height. It was just nice visuals, but in VR, it was just more personal, like I'm affected by the height. I mean, you're not, but it felt like it." (T1-P1, Div)

Q7: Quote: "Not necessarily, because, also, when you use a normal keyboard, at some point, you don't look at your hands anymore."

Q8: Quote: "Because I wonder why is there no VR Assassin's Creed? Actually, I think, isn't there VR?... There is, there is, okay. Because maybe I should try that now." (Cross-Cutting-P2)

Q9: Quote: "So, since there are much more sensors included in VR, you definitely get exhausted faster. Yeah, but not in a bad way. Just because you are just more engaged, in any case." (T2-P3)

Q10: Quote: "*The productivity, because you're just... everything is a bit more fast. [Identifying PC's distinguishing advantage]*" (T2-P2)

Q11: Quote: "Um, and what I wished was, um, that I get, for example, when I forgot, okay, this one robot there, did I already deactivate it or not? But when I pressed, uh, the button for this signal, it was still shown in red, like, all the others that might be already, um, still active... Um, so just an extra color indicator for this." (T5-P2, Design-05)

Q12: Quote: "Yes, but not because it was complicated designed, but because I need to remind myself that VR is actually so realistic, that you need to all the time adjust your hands to actually climb. It's, I was still used to pressing only one button. It was just this." (T4-P2)

Q13: Quote: "Uh, I guess, um, the PC version, everything, the whole, um, like, every mechanic. Um, also because, maybe it's just because of Unreal Engine, but, um, the gameplay of the PC version was very smooth, everything very, very nice, very same as well." (T4-P1)

Q14: Quote: "Um, the keyboard because, but I think only because on a regular basis I use the keyboard at home. Um, that's the only reason I feel I probably, if I used, um, a gaming console, um, a PlayStation or so, maybe I, I, then I wouldn't be used to the keyboard."

Q15: Quote: "I wouldn't mind getting used to... Motion controllers?... Yeah. Like, I would sacrifice the keyboard." (T2-P4)

Q16: Quote: "I just needed to get used to it, in, like, for the VR version, both worked fine in the end, after I got used to everything. I like to have all the most important buttons very close to my thumbs... the deactivating button for the robots, the oh shit button, basically. I wished it to be the one below... but, as I said, you got used to it."

Q17: Quote: "It's hard to tell. Mm-hmm. I guess, the VR version, just because, like, genre-wise, it's rather being sneaky, assassinating robots, and, that's why I want this mechanic of

looking around corners, and, I can't do that in PC versions... For example, if it was a strategic game, then I wouldn't care about the VR version... Genre makes a lot of difference." (T6-P1, T6-P2)

Q18: Quote: "Um, yes, like, I think there are some people who don't like the smooth rotation or smooth movement in general... Yes, I don't have a problem with it, but, um, maybe a suggestion... maybe even if you only move your head for some centimeters, maybe in VR, you turn around for, for even more degrees." (T3-P2, Design-03)

Q19: Quote: "Definitely, when I was almost shot, because the animation was like this, or, actually, I don't remember what it was, but this... But, in the right moment, I was able to disable him, and that it was frozen in this frame that I almost got shot was just very... How do you say? How do you say in English? Exciting? Thrilling? Dangerous? Yeah." (T1-P4)

Q20: Quote: "Just in more satisfying, because, yeah, because you, you need to do a whole movement with your hand instead of just pressing E or something." (T5-P1, Design-04)

Q21: Quote: "Yes, it was a bit more. I personally didn't like the way you, the locomotion, it was just, I mean, of course, you could also tilt your head and then you change direction as well. But, to be very fast, and sometimes you needed to be fast, maybe because of the robots, and then it was a bit annoying to change direction with, with, what was the, how was the button called, where you, thumbstick?... Right, thumbstick, thumbstick. Yeah, that's the only thing, the locomotion, otherwise, it was more satisfying in VR." (T3-P3, R5.2)

Q22: Quote: "So, it was a bit, of course, more demanding on the physical interactions for the VR. But, do you think it was also more satisfying?... Yeah... Because of that?... Yeah. I guess for me that's a good point." (T4-P3)

P04

Q1: Quote: "Yeah. That's better, and it is easier also to progress in the game for me. That is also another part. It is easier to, to play the game."

Q2: Quote: "Yes, it's almost the same, almost the same. Just because of being more, more, having better immersion in VR version, yeah, that's, that, that is the main, main difference."

Q3: Quote: "Well, for being more present and immersion, the VR one was better. I felt it much better, and maybe even it was a little bit too much sometimes. Because I'm not used to VR. So, yeah, I don't know what else I can add to it." (R5.1)

Q4: Quote: "Xbox controller was always ergonomic. That was, that is good... The other one, VR one, also, it felt good in my hands... It is almost similar, yeah."

Q5: Quote: "By, by, by, because I'm used to it. So, when I want to open a door, I press a button in a video game. When I want to go, like, for example, for a ladder, it depends on the game also. So, so, so, in some games, it's just a combination of first pressing a button and then going up or down... Uh, but overall, because I'm used to the non-VR version, that one was easier for me to get the control, to have the, uh, how to say, to implementation of the control was easier for me to understand." (T3-P3, T4-P1)

Q6: Quote: "I have some issues to understand how the controller works in VR because I'm not used to it."

Q7: Quote: "Well, I'm more curious to see how the VR version looks, okay? Well, I'm kind of, uh, I mean, I haven't much experience of VR, and I am also kind of curious to see how is this, how is this VR games?"

Q8: Quote: "I think VR version is more fun."

Q9: Quote: "So, I got too close to the wall and to the object, and being too much close doesn't have a much good feeling to me."

Q10: Quote: "So, overall, the VR is, the VR version is, isn't, doesn't have that much of convenience or easy... One of the examples, what the interaction that I want to mention, or I also want to mention, is that the, the, the way that you can move the camera. Or, in point of view, in the VR version. You, it was, like, based on some degree, that you could, kind of, move it. But I would, maybe, maybe it was easier to have more freedom when you want to move the camera, with the right stick."

Q11: Quote: "But I think that is even, that can even make the VR part more challenging for me, because I'm not used to VR. Maybe for someone who is more used to VR, it can be more entertaining to do it like a real world."

Q12: Quote: "Mm-hmm, like, in non-VR, I felt that, for example, one of the texts, I felt that is, too long, and, I felt that, there could be, maybe, sometimes, a better way of showing, what you, what you can do, or, what you should do in the game, or, what's better to do, also, VR version, similarly."

Q13: Quote: "At first, I had dizziness... After some time, I got used to it. It became much better."

Q14: Quote: "It was that you feel that you are doing something similar to a real world when you want to press a button. So, I think this one was good."

Q15: Quote: "With the VR one, it was more challenging because I'm not, I'm not used to. But also, it has the entertaining part also. So, so, the way of doing the interaction in VR, not maybe for, but overall, it was, uh, entertaining process." (T4-P3)

Q16: Quote: "On the non-VR version, that was just with button, and you could, it was, it was, how to say, it was a more familiar experience to me. I'm kind of being used to that one, and that was easier, but on the VR, it was more difficult, and at first, it wasn't that much of a good feeling. Maybe a little later, it got better." (T4-P2)

Q17: Quote: "Because you are imagining that you are in that world and you are part of the world. So, this feel is better presented in the VR version [Talking about interactions]." (T1-P3)

Q18: Quote: "Yeah. So, if I want to say about the interaction, if you are going to consider just by convenience, the non-VR. It's much easier. Much easier. But if you want to think about immersion and entertainment, then the VR version could be more entertaining."

Q19: Quote: "Sometimes it was overwhelming. So, it was overwhelming sometimes. Not all the times. Sometimes, and I just wanted, for example, to slide a little to left and right... I couldn't do that easily. So, this was challenging. It is repetitive. I'm sorry that I'm saying. Also, the ladder part was challenging."

Q20: Quote: "Well, at first, I had dizziness. It was more, my dizziness was more, and it was a, a bit challenging for me. After some time, I got used to it. It became much better. But then, after some time, I got a little bit tired." (T2-P1)

Q21: Quote: "Well, in the VR one, I wanted to use the ladder. So, I got too close to the wall and to the object, and being too much close doesn't have a much good feeling to me."

Q22: Quote: "Yeah, in the VR, the feeling, that feeling is more intense. That was more intense... So, in the normal game, or, I mean, not, sorry, sorry, in the non-VR. In the non-VR, it's not very, how to say, I mean, it is less intense, much, or maybe much less intense. But in the VR one, it is more intense." (T1-P2, T1-P4, Div)

Q23: Quote: "The lever also similar to that one. That one was maybe even better than the button. But I think for the button, that was done right and correctly. Lever. That one also was, like, similar to real world, and it was done in a good way, and it was convenient also." (T5-P1, Design-04)

Q24: Quote: "The implementation of the mechanics, like, how do you use a rope, how do you use a zipline, maybe, and, for example, how you push a button, press a button, and also the lever. These are better compared to the non-VR."

Q25: Quote: "So, the VR was more evident, the difference between heights. It was much more evident because of the depth that you can feel in the VR that you cannot feel it that much in non-VR version, and the dystopian part, well, I think similarly in the VR version, it was more, it was because of the embedded immersion. I think you could feel it more." (T1-P1)

Q26: Quote: "Well, I'm more curious to see how the VR version looks, okay? Well, I'm kind of, uh, I mean, I haven't much experience of VR, and I am also kind of curious to see how is this, how is this VR games?... So, if the convenience part and the comfort is same as the PC, then I will go with VR." (T2-P2, T6-P1)

Q27: Quote: "Like, you should get to that, kind of, cube thing, and touch that, and press that, and, um, I think, maybe, there can be a better alternative."

P05

Q1: Quote: "In general the headset didn't bother me at all so this was fine. I could have worn this for a while longer of course. This is not an issue."

Q2: Quote: "But for these levers I don't. So I don't... At least I don't mind as much."

Q3: Quote: "For the most part the Xbox controller also because of strafing because it's just a style that I play in. I'm basically never going in a straight line in a shooter type game. Also in a third person type game I'm probably also constantly doing the left and right thing around corners and stuff like that. So with that I was more used to it and it felt more like the default I'm used to." (T3-P1, Design-02)

Q4: Quote: "I would absolutely freaking love to play this in a big big hall. In a big room where I could actually walk all of the distance. This would be amazing I think."

Q5: Quote: "I think VR gives me a much better sense of scale. I realized that, no, I didn't realize, I noticed that kind of, I was kind of trying to look around much more in VR than I was in the, in the mouse and keyboard thing. So basically I was, in one place I was just standing there like looking over the level and being like, yeah, this is kind of a big area here that I get to occupy... There's just a stereoscopic view of something and the micro-movement that I get to do that gives me a sense of scale of the whole environment. I think that's much better in VR." (T1-P2)

Q6: Quote: "My first try was kind of going on the rungs, on the step things... you don't have to go either or. You could just offer both if you want."

Q7: Quote: "In the screen-based one, it's kind of just an animation that happens, and in VR, it's something where I feel like, oh, this is doing something to me. So, I kind of have like this feeling of being actually moved in some way. It doesn't really feel like on a slack line, yeah, for sure, but at least I have this feeling of, oh, yeah, something's happening here." (T1-P1)

Q8: Quote: "Like 20 minutes of VR gives me a very slight dizziness always. So this is not really tied to this experience but I had this here too. So I did have like this this moment where I'm like yeah I'm kind of it was enjoyable but I was also kind of glad that I now got to take off the headset again. Because I think if I think if it was twice as long I probably would have needed to pause at this point. So like after like half an hour or 45 minutes for sure I think I would have just needed a break." (T2-P1, T2-P2, T2-P3)

Q9: Quote: "The weird thing that, again like this takes me much better into the place and I'm embodying this avatar much better in VR. I still kind of have to think back at, yes, I have something in my hands that is buttons that I need to press... Because if you start thinking about the buttons then these are no longer my hands. In that moment these are my controllers and then I'm not really part of this world."

Q10: Quote: "I have a little bit of a caveat there because I'm very used to the Xbox controller. That is the layout that I'm very familiar with. It's the same one on the like Arrow GLI or on the Xbox that I play at home and stuff like that. So that is something where I know oh I press X. That's just memory. What's it called? Muscle memory basically, and on the quest controllers I constantly needed to read oh I press X for that. Oh where's X again? Oh it's over here." (T3-P3, T4-P1)

Q11: Quote: "Because if you start thinking about the buttons then these are no longer my hands. In that moment these are my controllers and then I'm not really part of this world."

Q12: Quote: "In German, you call this Produktsprache. So a product talking to you how it wants to be used. For example, this bottle, it's very clear that I kind of... It's made for my hand. I can grab it or I have this handle here... The product tells me how it wants to be used, and in VR, you get the same thing. So if you haven't looked at stuff like Don Norman's The Design of Everyday Things, this is absolutely a book for you because I think real-world products and how they are designed, they can inform a lot about how you would design stuff in VR as well because it's the same thing."

Q13: Quote: "The headset was easier in one particular place because the balancing thing was much much easier. Because I had much finer control over like tenths of a degree of movement where I was actually going as compared to the controller. Also it's much more direct in that regard. So with the controller getting to the exact with the dead zone that the controller intrinsically has, and with the sensitivity setup that you will have it's you can get used to controllers but it's always kind of like a step in between, and I think the head movement is just hands down so much more precise and direct."

Q14: Quote: "My first try was kind of going on the rungs, on the step things. I think it's rungs, right? So I'm not sure if this is something worth adding, because you don't have to go either or. You could just offer both if you want. But I'm also not sure if I'm like the only person or if it's just something that's universal that people would try this." (T4-P2, Design-01)

Q15: Quote: "This is better I think because there's... Of course these are like pretty obviously interactable element big levers. So not like in a flat where it's like a dilly dilly switch on the wall or something. So you can recognize them from far. So I don't really have an expectation how these would feel, and in some regards I have like an expectation how a button should feel or react. But for these levers I don't. So I don't... At least I don't mind as much. I think

they were great. Also I think they had a little bit of amount of vibration going on, right?... I think this helps a little bit. These I would say work pretty well." (T5-P1, Design-04)

Q16: Quote: "I think it works, and probably the ladder tells you that it works too well. Or that you actually basically a little bit broke your own rule, and that it works so well that people started grabbing this ladder instinctively. But again, this is a pretty cool achievement already, I would say. Because I do think this is something we can absolutely learn from this." (T5-P3, R5.4)

Q17: Quote: "This is something there that I need, that I think needs a slight alteration because it does work, clearly it works, but I kind of want to look in the direction that I'm going. So I kind of need the button to be somewhere else or I need to be able to grab the rope and that starts the traveling process. I think this was my first try also to try to do the same thing as for the, for the other rope, basically trying to just grab there and hold the, the not shoulder button... The grab button, yeah."

Q18: Quote: "So for a demonstration of like 20 minutes I could choose either. I would probably choose VR for the novelty and for the slight edge on the immersion. If this was something like a 10 hour story game or something, I would probably at some point switch over to mouse and keyboard just because I can't play this for much longer without it being a problem for me." (T6-P1, Design-04)

Q19: Quote: "In the PC version it didn't stand out all that much. So basically, you have had ladders in games since Duke Nukem 3D or you have had things like these lines that you slide over in like a Tomb Raider... there was nothing where I would say, oh, this was beyond what I would usually get from a game. But also, hey, it was already pretty, pretty amazing from what I would get for a student project where usually you don't get around to all these details." (T6-P3)

Q20: Quote: "I would have preferred in both versions for the walking speed to be slightly higher. I think it's kind of it feels like a slow walk and in games like these in the in between spaces between two things that are happening I kind of would usually press shift and run a little bit of stuff like that."

Q21: Quote: "I do need some more feedback there. I do think that even like a slight vibration might help a little bit, but also kind of... I kind of want my hand to be stopped and I know that's not quite possible just now. But this kind of makes these interactions less satisfying that

I would like them to be, and again, that's not something that I would fault you personally for because you can't change physics and stuff... It sounds weird but I think it's half the fun of actually hitting something, and again, I don't have a solution there. I'm just saying why it sometimes doesn't quite work for me and beyond." (T5-P2, Design-05)

Q22: Quote: "I think I did this with the hands particularly. I'm not sure if I would have needed to. But it also kind of was something that I kind of felt I wanted to do. Like something where I would like need to grab the robot and do something to them. Even though I probably could have sat here and just trigger the button I'm not sure. But also with the representation of a virtual hand in there it kind of felt natural to kind of like do something to the robot somehow."

Q23: Quote: "At some point I kind of ran into this table a little bit so I was kind of close by and I wasn't sure which way to turn right now. So there was a little bit about the setup I would have preferred to have a little bit more space around me. I just kind of neglected to basically push back a little bit more before starting."

Q24: Quote: "Overall I can't really say it's a little bit of a toss up though. Mostly I think the Xbox controller came easier to me and this one place is much much better to control in a headset."

Q25: Quote: "I think this was my first try also to try to do the same thing as for the, for the other rope, basically trying to just grab there and hold the... grab button."

Q26: Quote: "For me personally, I would give a slight edge to the VR version because, in general, I can be very immersed in any type of screen-based gaming as well... In this particular case, for example, like looking over the edge of something that's a very steep fall I could fall down from. This is something that is definitely more. I feel this is more something that could happen to me in VR than in the keyboard and mouse or controller-based stuff. Also, basically, with a controller-based game, you don't get like this type of leaning forward looking over the edge and looking straight down." (T1-P3, Div)

Q27: Quote: "It took me a while in the controller based run. In the first run it took me a while to actually recognize oh I need to get to these robots from behind, and then basically I was kind of looking for not so much what's the active area of the robot. I was more looking like what do I need to aim at... by the time I got to the headset I already figured out how this works, and it was much easier to just sneak more or less sneak up on them."

Q28: Quote: "I think VR is sabotaged a little bit because by the time I got to VR I already understood that these basically don't pose a threat to me. So I think the very low difficulty and the getting used to where they are and having been through the level already... the VR run wasn't like sneaky spy exciting in any way. Because I already knew what the robots were doing but they basically are too dumb to really hurt me in any way." (Emrgent-P3)

P06

Q1: Quote: "It was like I am really interacting. It was not in a negative way but in a positive way—like I am actually interacting. For example, using the rope when I was interacting with it and going forward, it felt good, like I am interacting in the real world." (T1-P3)

Q2: Quote: "For the lift in VR, it was a bit awkward because it was shaking continuously from starting to end, and I didn't feel like using it."

Q3: Quote: "To be honest, nothing in particular. I think the things there are is already good, and nothing else should be added."

Q4: Quote: "In this case, it's of course PC because it was really easy for me to interact in PC. In some cases in VR, when I am interacting with the bots and we are face to face, I can't go behind it and disable him. So if he is facing me, it's certain that I am dying and re-spawning." (T3-P1, Design-01)

Q5: Quote: "It was really good because, for example, for the lift I had to pull the lever and then interact with the lift. I felt it was really good, and also for the button when I am pressing it and it works. Compared to the PC version, it felt good to me." (T5-P1, Design-04)

Q6: Quote: "I did use VR before, not on a regular basis, but I have used it to play video games. But I'm not fluent in that—I'm not regular there."

Q7: Quote: "I felt more present in the VR actually because I felt like the environment was created specifically for VR. Like, the environment when I look around and interactive objects like the ladder and other things, like interacting with the enemies also, it felt like it was made for VR and I enjoyed that." (T1-P1)

Q8: Quote: "From my previous experiences, I feel some motion sickness while moving. But in this case, I didn't feel that, to be honest. I actually didn't feel that. I moved smoothly and

rotated around. Even I looked down from the height—I have height phobia—so when I look down, I should have felt something, but I didn't." (T2-P1, Div)

Q9: Quote: "For the comfort one, I will say the PC. But for the interaction side, I will definitely say VR—it was really fun in VR interactions." (T2-P2, R5.1)

Q10: Quote: "Not really. I removed the headset and walked around here fine. I didn't feel anything."

Q11: Quote: "It really felt like it made a difference. The instructions were really good and specific. They didn't vary over time and stayed constant. It actually felt like, as you described, when I see things I know exactly what to do. So the instructions were really good." (T5-P3)

Q12: Quote: "For the movement, it is easier for me to control in PC, of course, as I play mostly in PC. (T4-P1) But in VR, I didn't feel like I am being stuck or I can't control the player at all—I didn't feel like that. But in some cases in VR, I couldn't find out which way to go." (T3-P3)

Q13: Quote: "I actually did in the VR version. I actually felt it, to be honest. For example, in the last section when I had to disarm the robots—that was an intense moment when there were three or four robots going around and I had to sit and go slowly to interact with them, to hide from them and to interact with them. That was quite a fascinating moment in that game which I didn't feel in the PC." (T1-P4)

Q14: Quote: "As I described earlier, in the last phase there were four robots I guess, and I had to sneak behind them to disable them. It felt like I failed two to three times, and then I had to use the sit button—I had to sit and look around using the sonar to find out where the enemy is going, and then I had to sneak behind them and disable them. It was quite fun actually."

Q15: Quote: "What was the most memorable moment in the PC version?"... "Overall it was good, but nothing specific." (T6-P3)

Q16: Quote: "When I was playing it, I felt like if it was a night environment, it will feel really good—like the Batman games."

Q17: Quote: "In the VR, I guess. It's more satisfying. For PC, it's normal interaction things, but for VR it's always new—it's always something new."

Q18: Quote: "Kind of like that, exactly. Because when I was using the zipline, I was looking around, looking below, seeing the scenario overall, and it felt good."

Q19: Quote: "To be honest, when I was playing in PC, that height didn't matter actually, to be honest. But for the VR version, I felt it—really felt it, like when I'm going up and looking down from the high height, and the environment was really great, and I felt that height comparison in the VR actually." (T1-P2)

Q20: Quote: "Will you be willing to sacrifice the comfort... to play the VR version?"... "I definitely will." (T2-P4)

Q21: Quote: "I'll definitely go with the VR version... Because it is interactive. I felt like interacting with everything there is, and it felt fun. It felt interactive, and the last part with the bots, it felt really good and really challenging, and I didn't feel that in PC. So I'll definitely choose the VR." (T6-P1, R5.5)

Q22: Quote: "After trying both versions, would you be interested in playing more VR games?"... "Yeah, I would be."... "Mostly for the interaction parts." (Cross-Cutting-P2)

Q23: Quote: "I can play for an hour in PC, of course. But for VR, I guess half an hour or less, I guess." (T2-P3)

Q24: Quote: "The PC version was usual—as I am just interacting with it and going up, nothing fancy. But for the VR version, I was a bit confused why I am holding the side bars and going up instead of holding the steps and going up. So it was new to me, to be honest." (T4-P2, Design-01)

Q25: Quote: "Because when I was using the zipline, I was looking around, looking below, seeing the scenario overall, and it felt good."

Q26: Quote: "Can you name any particular thing that you felt the VR version did way better than the PC version?... I guess there are multiple—the ladder system, the zipline system, and the rope also (Despite Ladder Mechanics Confusion)." (T4-P3)

P07

Q1: Quote: "I have to say yes. Genre matters, I think. Because when I'm actually going to, going on, you know, the racing games or FPS shooting games or something like that, in that case, I think I would be really comfortable in Windows games than VR." (T6-P2)

Q2: Quote: "Just the movement. Like I was free. I was free in the game, and, you know, the rest of the things I think VR was pretty good, but the overall experience, so all of it, like, when you combine, like, the smoothness of Windows was way better." (T2-P2, T3-P3)

Q3: Quote: "I think if I talk about immersiveness, in this case, I have to say, you know, the Windows game, you know, the PC gave me the better version when I'm like pulling the ladders. With VR, it was, I think I felt like I'm, it was sort of pulling the ladder. However, I didn't feel that good in VR, you know, when I'm pulling the ladder... But the experience with a PC was really good because, you know, you just went there, you press the button and while like pressing on the button, you just got, the experience was really smooth."

Q4: Quote: "If I'm thinking about any functionality, it could be, and every, if I talk about, you know, specific functionality, every functionality is better in VR, you know, the experience... But the overall experience is way much better in Windows, just because, you know, I think the design, game design... It's how I play the game in general, and the game design for VR wasn't really good." (Cross-Cutting-P1, R5.2)

Q5: Quote: "Uh, I think, there is no, you know, the PC version hadn't anything which is, you know, I remember properly, like, there was severe difference than the VR. However, the overall experience was really smooth." (T6-P3)

Q6: Quote: "I think for me the presence was more, you know, I felt the presence significantly in VR. However, if I talk about, you know, the comfort or immersiveness or that aspect, I think it was better in Windows PC. However, the presence, you know, itself, I mean, this game, I'm inside this game, this feelings was better in VR." (T1-P1)

Q7: Quote: "Even when climbing the ladder, sometimes my body was touching the ladder, and I wasn't really trying to do that, you know... I think if there was an animation there, and the experience was sort of similar to windows. That it's happening very smoothly up and down in the VR, then the VR implementation would be better than the Windows version."

Q8: Quote: "I think, like when I played other games in VR, where I personally had the control to go, you know, move left or right, and it wasn't really present there, and I was always going forward and backward and moving with this, and it wasn't really, I mean, I wanted the right and left movement. I think if I had left and right movement, I would have chosen VR over Windows game for this project." (T3-P1, Design-02)

Q9: Quote: "No, not only rotation, the game itself, all the controls. Like you can't really move forward or backward or move left or right. For five seconds, plus forward and backward for two to three seconds, and next you're again on, and in between that time, I was getting caught by the AI. So which made me frustrated a little bit."

Q10: Quote: "Did you experience any motion sickness, nausea or any kind of dizziness, eye strain during the VR gameplay?"... "No."... "Was everything good?"... "Everything was good." (T2-P1)

Q11: Quote: "Exactly that, that experience, and I was going, I think from, at first, I made a mistake when I tried it from the first time, because I really didn't understand it quite. So, at that time, I sort of swung backward. But after that, I always used the rope technique, you know, the properly, in the forward, forward way, and it was really good, the experience was good. But the first one wasn't, that's the thing." (T4-P3)

Q12: Quote: "I think height wasn't actually that kind of an issue to talk about because I didn't really feel anything like significant here. Like, that's something I have to talk about. I think it was all quite normal." (Div)

Q13: Quote: "The thing is, the Windows version was better... Then it, and I think the reason behind this is that I'm really much more comfortable with Windows version as I'm playing it. I think I was in, I think my age was four, three or four when I first started to play computer games. So, I think there's a comfort, of course." (T4-P1)

Q14: Quote: "I think height wasn't actually that kind of an issue to talk about because I didn't really feel anything like significant here."

Q15: Quote: "I would, I would try it on VR... There is lag, but if I don't have a lag and I can move left and right, I think I have to go with the VR version." (Div)

Q16: Quote: "I think if I had left and right movement, I would have chosen VR over Windows game for this project."

Q17: Quote: "For five seconds, plus forward and backward for two to three seconds... in between that time, I was getting caught by the AI."

Q18: Quote: "Every functionality is better in VR... But the overall experience is way much better in Windows."

Q19: Quote: "However, if someone is not really used to with VR, and he doesn't, I think there's an issue. I mean, if you just press a button here, then you could just swing from one place to another backwards, or the position you're looking at. So, you have to be really subtle about it, like where you're looking at it, and if you have that, I think it's better than windows."

Q20: Quote: "It was natural, and, I think it's all of the functionalities there. Like, disabling the AI or everything. That was much more alive in the VR version." (T1-P3, T5-P1, Design-04)

Q21: Quote: "Yeah, I think it's the VR one. It's the VR one. I felt more alive there." (T1-P4)

Q22: Quote: "I think if there was an animation there, and the experience was sort of similar to windows... then the VR implementation would be better than the Windows version."

P08

Q1: Quote: "Definitely I felt more anxious because, because yeah, it was very up close with the robots... it felt like a little bit of threatening, like more threatening than the non-VR version." (T1-P4)

Q2: Quote: "Yes, yes, definitely more engaging but it was also more difficult."

Q3: Quote: "Um, I think it would have been better if i took some rest."

Q4: Quote: "For this game, um, uh, okay, uh, first, firstly I think, um, when I, uh, used the sonar like it pinpointed the location objectives for me. So those were very, uh, very small green cubicle things. So, I think, I at first, I had a little bit of problems with finding those because, um, and, I believe I didn't find any clear instructions or maybe I've missed it. But I think the objectives should be marked a little more like, um, visible or like more prominent to the gamer."

Q5: Quote: "Um, if it's in terms of presence, uh I think the VR version was more appropriate to me. Um, I think um the first question was which version do I prefer and I think there are certain circumstances or certain points in which I think uh both of the VR and non-VR version have their advantages and disadvantages. So in terms of presence I think I prefer the VR version because in that version I feel more immersed and sort of like more present there."
(T1-P1)

Q6: Quote: "Definitely, the VR one, because when I press the button, and the zipline starts, and sort of like my camera was on the opposite direction. So when I moved my head and it felt like, I am on the zipline, so it was immersive, so yeah."

Q7: Quote: "For me, it is the interesting part, like I said in the comparison earlier, like a very normal thing in a non-VR game can be a very interesting thing in a VR game, and that is the first time I'm experiencing this." (Cross-Cutting-P2)

Q8: Quote: "Yes, I was definitely a little bit confused because, um, I believe there were no like text based or clear instructions when i was climbing the ladder, and as someone who haven't played many VR games for me that was new. So yeah it was a little confusing for me at the first, at the beginning." (T4-P2, Design-01)

Q9: Quote: "Um, yes definitely the perception was a bit different. Um, I felt like um when i was playing in the non-VR version for me it was um mostly all the areas felt a little bit similar to me. But when i played on the VR version, I sort of felt the differences a little bit more in general. Like I used to pinpoint certain areas like okay this is a little bit different than the other. But in the non-VR version more or less the areas felt a little bit of similar to me."
(T1-P2)

Q10: Quote: "Definitely, yeah. The years of experience of playing video games, that's definitely there." (T4-P1)

Q11: Quote: "Would you have preferred that you could move just like you move in the PC version, in the VR too? Rather than having this head-based movement would you have preferred to move like a normal controller thumbstick movement, left right, and forward, and backward in any direction?... Uh, I think that would have been, um, much more easier to control I think. Because that's the control scheme that, uh, we usually use in non-VR games. So for me, I think, uh, I think that would have been a better experience for me personally."
(T3-P1, Design-02)

Q12: Quote: "Yeah, so um, um again I would say like in the non-VR version it was like, uh, effortless... but in the VR version there were a lot of this interactable moment in which you have to do certain actions. In each of these um individual moments you have to do different sort of action. Like for the lever you have to pull it up, for the button you have to press it down. So you're sort of using your gesture, you're using your hands, you're using that to do it... So, um, in terms of experience these are, I think they are, these are, um, little experiences but i think these are very fun experiences." (T1-P3, T5-P1, Design-04)

Q13: Quote: "Um, definitely the non-VR version was easier. Because, um, once again I have, uh, familiarities with the controls with the gamepad or with the non-VR games. So like it was, um, sort of like a muscle memory to me. So I didn't have much difficulties controlling the player with the controller. But in the VR version again I had to learn a lot of things. Um, there is nothing in my muscle memory. So the camera movement and the, uh, the rotational movement and the character movement, I had a little difficulty with the synergies, to perform the synergies with those things." (T3-P3, R5.3)

Q14: Quote: "I think the objectives should be marked a little more like, um, visible or like more prominent to the gamer."

Q15: Quote: "So climbing a ladder after playing this game in the VR version, before playing this game I did not have thought that climbing a ladder would be this much you know, uh, impactful or you have to put a lot of effort in this. So this was a new experience for me definitely, and um yeah definitely it was fun, it was fun, and also like when i had to put an effort on this particular action it felt a lot more meaningful for me. So yeah definitely it was a good experience. I had to learn first, I was failing a lot, but when i finally did it that was a very good feeling of accomplishment, yeah." (T4-P3, R5.6)

Q16: Quote: "Well, I, uh, no not necessarily, but I felt a little bit of weight on my head and a little bit of eye strain. Because, I think, I, um, sort of like messed up with the focus thing, I felt like I did it well. But at some points some particular angles or some particular things did become a little bit of blurry. But, um, those are not very big issues, very small issues. But overall, yes I had a very good experience, nothing that severe." (T2-P1)

Q17: Quote: "Um, I think I would choose the VR version, because I had more fun playing it, and also the sense of immersion, I think works better with the VR version than the non-VR version." (T6-P1, R5.5)

Q18: Quote: "So in the VR version I believe there are things that um when you interact with it gives you a more purposeful behavior."

Q19: Quote: "So, do you think you kind of like went, uh, around 40 minutes in the VR version straight. Do you think it was fine or do you think it would have been better if you could take some rest in between?... Um, I think it would have been better if i took some rest."
(T2-P3)

Q20: Quote: "Um, I think at first I need to experience that myself, because I don't know, if like, uh, people get dizzy or motion sickness in general, in that smooth camera movement. But I think I would have preferred the smooth camera movements. Definitely, yeah." (T3-P2, Design-03)

Q21: Quote: "It depends I believe, it depends. Um, I think VR can definitely be immersive, but I don't think it can be immersive in every bit of genre, I believe. I think VR has sort of like a particular genre of video games that can feel very immersed with VR definitely. But there are also a lot of different type of video games or genres, which I believe a lot of players are, including me would prefer non-VR or just normal desktop version." (T6-P2)

Q22: Quote: "Um, I think accessibility, that like I've speaking about it a lot, because, uh, and also, um, yeah the accessibility the first thing. Because the control schemes and the tasks are like, those are very easy to do and you don't have to like look around and find stuff. You can just you know use your right stick to like control the camera and everything. So basically, um, it's a very relaxed way to play a video game, like the non-VR version was a very relaxed way." (T2-P2)

Q23: Quote: "But in the VR, the one thing that was very interesting to me was like, I can sort of like peek behind a wall and sort of can see, like the enemy can't see me but I can see the enemy. In the non-VR version i don't believe you can do that. So that part was really interesting to me. When I found out this feature, I used it, and I think this was very interesting. Like I can see the enemy and I can track his movement."

Q24: Quote: "So, um, in a lot of segments like where I have to like disable a particular robot, i have to move in a certain way to get behind that robot. So in the VR version I had some difficulties like, I have to, um, you know like move my head, and also rotate the camera and then move forward. So those things were a little bit of difficult for me but I enjoyed it, I enjoyed it."

P09

Q1: Quote: "No, it was pretty much like a moderate experience, nothing extreme." (T2-P1)

Q2: Quote: "There's a few different factors here. On the VR version, to be able to physically test the interactable items in the game, that was great. But due to like a long familiarity with controls in the PC version, that was like too easy to control... Yes. Right." [confirming ease was higher in PC but enjoyment was higher in VR]

Q3: Quote: "I think that was necessary. You kind of get tired moving your hands in a specific motion."

Q4: Quote: "Because like, I haven't played any VR games in this genre and this felt like, really, really interesting compared to what I've played on PC so far for the same genre."

Q5: Quote: "I think I would be inclined towards the VR version, mostly because how you like perceive the environment and mostly how it feels to be up close and personal with the game. So, for example, you can see your hands in the game. That's like one step into immersion. So, you have to physically touch the bots to disable them, whereas on the PC version you don't have that. So, that's kind of like a huge difference between the desktop and the VR version." (T1-P1)

Q6: Quote: "Yeah, that helps with motion sickness for me... Yeah, I would not prefer that [smooth rotation]. I'm more inclined towards using snap and like, for smaller adjustment, I can just move myself." (T3-P2, Design-03)

Q7: Quote: "As I said earlier, because of the hands, how you interact with the environment, that's the main focus... Yeah, definitely. It's like a whole different game."

Q8: Quote: "On the VR version you also have like a sense of scale. So, overall pacing, you can like go through the PC version easily, but on VR your brain kind of tricks you to take it slow and be careful. So, yeah, the VR." (T1-P2, Div)

Q9: Quote: "Because the poles were gray and the rungs were yellow, but on the other cases, everything that's yellow is interactable, but on the ladder it's not... Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first." (T5-P2, T5-P3, Design-01, R5.4, Design-05)

Q10: Quote: "I think that was necessary. You kind of get tired moving your hands in a specific motion."

Q11: Quote: "I would say like not being able to move left to right on the VR version, that's the only thing." (T3-P1, Design-02)

Q12: Quote: "The VR version... It's generally more enjoyable." (T6-P1)

Q13: Quote: "I think an hour at most." (T2-P3)

Q14: Quote: "Because like, I haven't played any VR games in this genre and this felt like, really, really interesting compared to what I've played on PC so far for the same genre, and this gives you like, more, better feelings." (T6-P2)

Q15: Quote: "Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first." (T4-P2)

Q16: Quote: "It really generally takes more effort, that I can say... I think positive way that like gives lasting impression... Yeah, definitely [a sense of achievement]." (R5.6)

Q17: Quote: "Uh, so in the VR version, I cared for the player. So, when he got shot or like got into sticky situations, then yeah, that felt like I was in the player's shoes. So, that felt personal. But on the PC version, I didn't care if he died or what or like if I lost. So, I didn't care anything." (T1-P4)

Q18: Quote: "Well, it's like a totally different experience, especially the lever. I like that, and pressing down on things like that gives you like a very good immersion... Yeah, definitely [natural to see button and press it]." (T1-P3, T5-P1, Design-04)

Q19: Quote: "PC was easier to learn... Just because like, it's the familiar layout for PC. So, you kind of expect which button to do what, but in VR, that's more like real life. But in this game, yes, there is like a, you expected something to do, some kind of interaction then it did." (T3-P3, T4-P1)

Q20: Quote: "Climbing the ladder, because it was like a linear action."

Q21: Quote: "In VR, they are definitely scarier... It seemed generally straight-forward to me."

Q22: Quote: "Yeah. Turns out it's very much fun to climb ladders in VR." (T4-P3)

Q23: Quote: "So, will you be willing to sacrifice comfort of playing in a PC to enjoy the immersion in VR?... Yes." (T2-P4)

Q24: Quote: "Um, I would say restricted, like in a mental sense, because like, it kind of feels like you're there. So, yeah."

P10

Q1: Quote: "I would say the rope climbing. Though, it was stressing in the beginning, when I completed it, I was very satisfied. Like, I was very satisfied with my accomplishment."

Q2: Quote: "Though, I was a bit confused on where to grab when I was trying to grab it for the first time."

Q3: Quote: "I would say the rope in VR. I was having a hard time because the rope got inside my player and it was uncomfortable. At times, I wouldn't see what was in front properly and I also had a hard time grabbing the rope on the next position."

Q4: Quote: "I would say the controls were much easier to get a grasp on PC. It was not because the VR had bad controls, but rather because I'm more familiar with the layout on PC. I also love the head-based movement in VR, but I would have preferred if the rotation was smooth rather than snapping to certain degrees." (T3-P2, Design-02, Design-03)

Q5: Quote: "When I was like disabling the robots they still showed red on my sonar scan, which confused me a bit."

Q6: Quote: "One particular scenario that I remember was, when I was like disabling the robots they still showed red on my sonar scan, which confused me a bit. I would say a different color would be great to indicate the player, which robot is deactivated or which is not." (T5-P2, Design 05)

Q7: Quote: "The VR version felt more real because of the depth. In VR, I felt the heights in a more realistic way." (Div, No mention of fear)

Q8: Quote: "In VR, I actually cared about not getting caught or shot by the robots, probably because I felt more present in the world in VR."

Q9: Quote: "Mostly no, though I felt a bit dizzy after I took off the VR headset from my head, probably because my eyes were still adjusting." (T2-P1)

Q10: Quote: "The rope got inside my player and it was uncomfortable. At times, I wouldn't see what was in front properly."

Q11: Quote: "When I did it for a number of times, it was more fun to do in VR."

Q12: Quote: "I would have preferred if the rotation was smooth rather than snapping to certain degrees."

Q13: Quote: "Definitely the VR one, because it gave me a feeling as if I was present inside the game. It definitely felt more real and I enjoyed it more." (T1-P1)

Q14: Quote: "PC version provided me more freedom to explore the surroundings, because again, I am more familiar with the PC controls. So it naturally came to me and I wasn't stressed about it, the controls at all. It was like mostly muscle memories kicking." (T3-P3)

Q15: Quote: "The VR version was more stressing due to the scale of the surroundings. For some reason, in the PC version, dying or getting caught wasn't that stressing. But in VR, I actually cared about not getting caught or shot by the robots, probably because I felt more present in the world in VR." (T1-P4)

Q16: Quote: "Definitely, it's the VR, because of the scale that you can feel in the environment, the ladder, the rope, the zipline, everything felt like, life-like, because of the scale according to the real human. The height of the robot, the depth that I would feel while looking down from buildings felt like very real, which resulted in better embodiment of the character." (T1-P2)

Q17: Quote: "I would again say PC as I'm quite familiar with the layout of the PC version. I am probably a bit biased towards it." (T4-P1)

Q18: Quote: "It's a complicated question. I would say VR, if there wasn't any comfort related issue while playing the game, because I enjoyed VR more. But if we are talking about playing longer sessions, I would go with PC version for the comfort." (T6-P1, R5.1)

Q19: Quote: "I would say interactions. In the PC version, the interactions were something that I have done many, many times in other games, and it just didn't feel that different. The

VR version, however, is another story. I loved on how physical and life-like the experience was. I honestly, like, enjoyed it more." (T6-P3)

Q20: Quote: "My answer would be the same. Though I struggled a lot with the rope, I finally completed it after seven to eight tries and it was quite satisfying. It demanded a lot of physical effort, which was at times stressing, but really entertaining in the end." (T4-P3, R5.6)

Q21: Quote: "In this case, I would again vote for VR, because of the realism and physicality. I enjoyed pushing the buttons and pulling the lever, because I found a lot of similarities on how you do it in this real life. So definitely, I, it was more enjoyable in VR than PC." (T5-P1, Design-04)

Q22: Quote: "I think it depends on the genre of the game. If the game has a lot of physical reactions like this one, then I would sacrifice the comfort to enjoy VR's immersion." (T2-P4, T6-P2)

Q23: Quote: "Climbing the ladder, like, physically was more fun because I felt like I was actually doing something rather than controlling a character in a game. So I would vote for the VR in this case." (T1-P3)

Q24: Quote: "I can play on the PC version for at least a couple of hours while on the VR, it would mostly be around 40 to 45 minutes. Though, I enjoyed VR more, and my session was a bit longer than 45 minutes, I was feeling a bit tired." (T2-P2, T2-P3)

Q25: Quote: "I enjoyed the ladder, though, like, I got confused when where to hold on the ladder at the start of the game." (T4-P2, Design-01)

Q26: Quote: "I think physical crouching would have been more enjoyable and interactive, but as there was indeed a lot of crouching while playing the game, I personally think I wouldn't have been able to play the game for a long time in VR while crouching and standing all the time. So the experience of playing the game would have been more stressing rather than being entertaining and fun."